

The Concept of Discourse Analysis in Linguistics Artistic Discourse and Discourse Analysis

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ABSTRACT: In the world of linguistics, the term “discourse” is often used in many scientific works devoted to the study of text problems. As V. Hegay rightly points out, although the term is widely used in text linguistics as well as in the fields of literature, sociology, political science, philosophy, logic, psychology, text linguistics itself has a unique, widely accepted interpretation, meaningless, used to express a variety of different concepts.

KEYWORDS: literature, sociology, political science, philosophy, logic, psychology, text, syntactic complex, monologue sentence, communicative block.

INTRODUCTION

Initially, the terms “discourse” and “text” were used for the same concept, but later “text” was used for written communication and “discourse” for oral communication. For example, Dutch linguists T.A. van Dyke and W. Kinch use the term “discourse” as a synonym for “related speech”, noting that in recent years there has been a growing interest in the study of related speech or discourse in a number of humanities and social sciences [2.153-211 p]. Related speech, of course, means text, and it seems that the terms “text” and “discourse” are used interchangeably. It is also common to use the terms “text” and “discourse” to refer to different concepts. Researchers say that in French philology the term “discourse” is used in four different senses [3.143-144 p].

As A.I. Gorshkov pointed out, in the linguistic literature the term “discourse” does not have a definite meaning, it is used to describe a wide range of events, from “part of the text” to the whole “speech”. The word means “discourse” in French [4.39 p]. He notes that the word “discourse” can be a term meaning “part of a text”, but it is used in many linguistic literatures where the problem of text is studied from different perspectives”, “ Sentence ”, “ prosaic stanza ”, “ syntactic complex ”, “ monologue sentence ”, “ communicative block ”, etc., emphasizes that there is no need for the term “ discourse ”.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Two factors are important in the process of discourse research: the component of the discourse and the extent to which it is understandable to the listener (i.e., the listener’s process of understanding the term or phrase used in the speech process). In addition, another important factor is the same text that occurs in the process of speech activity. Discourse, like other language units, has character traits that are specific to a particular language.

Naturally, the participation of three main elements in the occurrence of any verbal communication is mandatory, namely, the speaker (writer) - information (text) - listener (reader). True, the role of speech conditions, information channel (such as voice, text, magnetic recording, telephone), status, age and other characteristics of communication members, as well as various other non-linguistic means in speech communication is extremely important, even often decisive. But these three elements are the main pillars of verbal communication, without which the process of communication cannot take place.

Linguistics naturally focused on the issue of linguistic expression and comprehension of information, which is the main subject of “giving and receiving” between the two parties (speaker, listener) in the same process of communication. After all, the ultimate and main goal of any communication is the “movement” of this information, and this “movement” is through language. That is why linguistics sought the basic and great unity of the same “information in motion”, as a result of which speech has long been recognized as such a great unity.

Emil Benvenist, a linguist who introduced the concept of discourse to science, argued that the term refers to the speaker’s speech process. His interpretation recognized that discourse is formed precisely in speech activity and expresses the knowledge

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and skills of the speaker, as well as that his place in society can be shaped by his life position (Benvenist 1974). From his point of view, the linguist prefers to approach the process of discourse analysis, taking into account its functional features. He entered linguistics in 1952. The concept of discursive analysis introduced by Horison emphasized the importance of not only phonetic or syntactic features in the text but also cultural heritage and values in the analysis process. In the process of analysis, he also noted that the structure of the discourse is of special importance. Later, in the 1950s, it was pointed out by many linguists that the term discourse was directly related to text linguistics. As a result of these assertions in linguistics, some different aspects of discourse and text become apparent. In particular, if the text is a stereotyped structure of the same style with an intangible structure, discourse occurs in the process of speech and learns that the changes that occur in the human mind are related to extralinguistic factors.

Another representative of discursive analysis is the Dutch linguist T.A. van Dyke also offered a number of his comments to science on the subject. According to Van Dyke, the discursive analysis covers 2 main stages.

- The process of analysis should cover the structural features of the text, ie the stage from phonetics to syntax
- Context analysis. An important aspect of discursive analysis is that the structural nature of the text reveals its main character aspects.

French linguist Elizabeth Le suggests considering discursive analysis in 3 stages.

1. In terms of the expression of language
2. According to the formation of views in society
3. According to the characteristics of communication between social groups and people

In cognitive analysis, the study of methods and tools surrounding mechanisms that reveal the linguistic expression of logical structures that occur in the process of knowing the world comes to the fore. It is known that a person performs an activity that has a number of logical and spiritual actions in knowing and perceiving things and objects, phenomena. "First of all, an object is studied in a live observation, by direct observation, and its properties, aspects, and aspects are determined, as a result of which properties, evidence, and events are collected and sorted. There is a need to move to the method of mental dialectical analysis" [1.50 p]. Several stages of the implementation of this mental analysis (activity in the logical-spiritual movement) are listed in a number of sources. According to them, in the activity of mental analysis, a certain object is initially distinguished from other objects. At the same time, of course, its distinctive features are taken into account. On the basis of distinctive signs, a comparative action is performed with another object, and an emotional symbol of that object is formed in the memory. Similar aspects of this symbol with other symbols in the language are sought. In the last stage, the generalization of an important stage in the cognition of reality is carried out. All of these activities serve to form an understanding of the object. The concept, which is the result of logical activity, generalizes with image and linguistic meaning ensures the emergence of the concept being studied as a key figure in cognitive linguistics networks.

As discussed above, it is difficult to say which factor is important, or which one is less important, when considering discursive analysis divided into 3 main stages. Because there are no significant differences between them that contradict each other. It should be noted that the process of cognitive research of discourse requires researchers to conduct their research in a variety of disciplines. This is because the concept of discourse is not limited to the field of linguistics, but has an interdisciplinary connection, and it should be noted that discursive analysis is an intermediate concept that is directly related to semiotics, ethnography, psychology, pragmatology and a number of other disciplines. However, it should be noted that most of the research related to the analysis of discourse in the above disciplines is related to the field of linguistics. According to T.A. van Dyke, scientific works devoted to the cognitive analysis of discourse differ from each other by the method chosen by the researcher, the field of science, and his individuality. T.A. van Dyke considers cognitive discursive analysis in two stages. That is, text analysis is a step-by-step study of the phonetic, orthographic structure of a text, as well as its morphological aspects, the syntactic features of sentences, and the place of units that have semantic and lexical meanings. The second stage is contextual analysis, which examines the social relations of events, time, space, time, participants, their cognitive characteristics.

Italic, embossed fonts, or letters of various shapes and colors are used to form information about the overall appearance of the discourse. This condition allows you to have an initial knowledge of exactly one text. We can see such views in more articles, newspaper ads, advertising banners. Syntactic structures have a number of unique constructions. T.A. van Dyke proposes an analysis of the unconventional syntactic construction in the selected text. That is, in many European languages, the article + noun (article + noun) is the traditional form and is defined on the basis of grammatical rules, so this situation does not apply to the analysis [2.153-211 p].

In the lexical semantic analysis of discourse, it is important to reveal the essence of the lexical units used in the text. At this stage, the discourse requires consideration of the units of language that represent the significance of the event being represented or the character traits of the participant. For example, positive words are used to describe positive personal traits,

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and negative words are used to describe negative ones. T.A. van Dyke also emphasizes that the main component of any text is the means of language expression. Exact means of expression serve as a basis for showing how reliable the text is and its relevance for the reader [2.153-211 p].

The process of discursive analysis requires a general approach to the text, not just to its structural features. Contextual analysis can be considered in several stages. These include setting, time, location, event / action, and participants. While the above steps are important, a more in-depth approach requires consideration of the following categories as well. That is, the domain, the role of the discourse participants, the social relations of the participants. When we consider the scope of activities, it is important to know in which area the parties to the dialogue are involved. For example, conversations of parliamentarians working in the political sphere may consist of terms, phrases, terms directly related to this field (political discourse), or the scope of teachers' activities will consist of phrases directly related to education (pedagogical discourse). It is obvious that each industry representative will be interviewed as part of their professional activities. There is also a general category for communicators, which includes the public sphere and the private sphere [2.153-211p]. Contextual analysis not only focuses on the role of participants in communication, their social relationships, or their cognitive character traits in a way that is different from the area in which participants operate. This aspect of the participants of the dialogue, that is, their purpose, opinion, beliefs, is important in the context analysis of the discourse. If these very aspects are ignored, the purpose for which the communication took place remains unclear. According to Van Dyke, the main role in revealing the character traits of communication participants is played by their social views, knowledge, skills and abilities.

The concept plays an important role in the cognitive analysis of discourse. The concept combines both cultural and cognitive factors. Cognitively, the concept reflects all the mental information in the human mind, and this information is formed directly through cultural heritage, national pride, national consciousness. Context plays an important role in revealing the character traits of a concept. The role of language units in expressing the concept in the text itself is invaluable.

Moem's story "Louise" depicts a man who thinks only of himself. It is through this story that we can consider the analysis of the concept of selfish. In Uzbek and English, the word has a negative connotation. If we look at the English interpretation of the above word 1) holding one's self interest as standard for decision making, 2) to put one's interest and benefit in the first place and to think only about himself or herself. In the process of cognitive analysis of the word selfish, we can encounter many other meanings: egoistic, greedy, miserly, hoggish, mean, narrow, stingy, mercenary, egocentric, ungenerous, prejudiced. The protagonist of the story, Louise, suffered from measles as a child and her heart was weak, so her parents did not believe her. He was protected from any hard work. Louise's selfishness is evident in her lifestyle, her attitude toward those around her, and herself. "I knew Luise before she married. She was then a frail, delicate girl with large and melancholy eyes. Her father and mother adored and worshipped her, for some illness, scarlet fever, had a left her with a weak heart and she had to take the greatest care of herself. I had noticed that if the party was amusing she could dance till five in the morning, but if it was dull she felt very poorly and Tom had to take her home early. On one occasion seeing her walk eight miles on an expedition that she especially wanted to make, I remarked Tom that she was stronger than one would have thought. He told her that I had remarked on her endurance "I shall pay for it tomorrow I shall be at death's door" she said to me ". Louise's selfishness was evident in her every move, but in the process she was so humble and helpless that she felt sorry for those around her: lifestyle: she was quite lost without a man to take care of her, and she didn't know how with her delicate health she was going to bring up her dear Iris; behavior: for the next two or three years Luise managed in spite of her weak heart, to go beautifully dressed to all the most lively parties, to gamble very heavily, to dance and even to flirt with tall slim young man; character: she disliked me and I knew that behind my back she seldom lost the opportunity of saying a disagreeable thing about me. she had too much delicacy ever to make direct statement but with a hint and a sigh and a little gesture of her beautiful hands she was able to make her meaning plain; speech: I shan't live to trouble you long. It can't be very long now, I'll try not to be troublesome, you always speak as though you grudged me the few years that I can expect to live; position: in order to distract her mind she turned her villa at Monte Carlo into a hospital for convalescent officers. Her friends told her that she would never survive the strain. She was lunching at a restaurant with a tall and very handsome young Frenchman. She explained that she was there on business connected with the hospital. She told me that the officers were very charming to her. They were how delicate she was and they wouldn't let her do a single thing. In the process of reading the story, we see that Louise is directly responsible for the fact that she is a selfish, self-centered person. He was so selfish that even some of the behaviors of his second wife, George, who cared for him, angered him. George didn't have the textual will like her first husband, he was tired of Louise's behavior. Luckily for Louise, the war broke out and George returned to military service and died three months later. How could Louise with a sick heart have endured a second loss? Artistic discourse is important to have a complete understanding of a concept. In the above story, we can see the potential of language means of expression in describing human character and revealing emotional state.

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CONCLUSION

There is another aspect that linguistics is interested in in the analysis of artistic discourse, and it has to be studied in two directions. First, the text of the work of art is used as a material for the study of language in synchronous and diachronic direction, the development of theoretical and practical foundations of linguistics, the study of its current or current state, the laws of development, scientific analysis of various categories. that is, it is used to determine the development of meaning. In this case, based on the goal set by the researcher, all units of language are covered and they are passed through a separate prism-stylistic prism. In the words of M.H. Kojina, this check penetrates vertically into language units. In these studies, it is not the primary meanings of language tools but their textual, additional meanings in speech that are explored and their methodological limitations depending on the tasks they perform.

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